

A Study of Visitors' on Destination Image, Environmental Perception, Travel Experiences and Revisiting Willingness in Xinshe Leisure Agriculture Park

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Abstract—The main purpose of this study is to analyze the relationship of leisure agriculture park visitors on tourist destination image, environmental perception, travel experiences and revisiting willingness. This study used questionnaires to Xinshe leisure agriculture park visitors' targeted convenience sampling manner total of 636 valid questionnaires. Valid questionnaires by descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and multiple regression analysis, the study found that: 1. The agricultural park visitors' correlations exist between the destination image, perception of the environment, tourism experience and revisiting willingness. 2."Excellent facilities and services", "space atmosphere comfortable" and "the spacious paternity outdoor space" imagery, of visitors' "revisiting willingness predict. 3. Visitors' in leisure agriculture park "environmental perception" and "travel experience, future revisiting willingness predict. According to the analysis of the results, the study not only operate on the recommendations of the leisure farm owners also provide follow-up study direction for future researchers.

Keywords—Leisure farms, image, travel experience, revisiting willingness, environmental perception.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN recent years due to the wide range of coping leisure travel demand leisure careers response to Taiwanese diversified leisure needs students, government counseling, for example, some of the traditional agricultural transformation of leisure agriculture driven Taiwanese another leisure travel patterns, was known as "rural tourism", "rural tourism", or "local tourism". Department of leisure agriculture to improve agricultural production structure, engaged in the production and marketing activities to improve the income of farmers, agricultural prosperity of the rural community, the adopted mode of operation. The one hand, it continues to maintain agricultural operations, on the other hand, provide recreational opportunities, so the combination of the characteristics of the primary industry and the tertiary industry, said that in recent years the development of new types of agricultural operations. Leisure Farm general recreation areas, has unique agricultural and cultural resources in rural areas, and different from the man-made natural rural landscape and become the most frequently chosen by the people in their weekly rest holiday leisure and recreational attractions; And part of the leisure farm for providing accommodation and catering services, have become major destinations of tourists travel. Leisure farm

operators in Taiwan, and is the most favorite destination of Taiwanese, one of the Xinshe leisure agriculture park. For the leisure farm operations, the visitors how select Xinshe leisure Agriculture Park as a tourist destination, visitors in mind why the farm cognitive and emotional evaluation, for the formulation of business strategy have an important role in the reference. Past research literature, tourism image and will affect the behavior of the visitors, and is often the basis for one of the tourists choose recreation areas [1]. More explicit, Baloglu [2] found that the tourism destination image, visitors to destination tourism for the first minor, plays an important role. According to Crompton [3] defined the image is the sum of certain objects, actions, and events held belief, impression, ideas and feelings. Crompton further pointed out that the main body of the image is, the people of the world a cognitive, and the imagery is to establish the basis of message processing of the human brain, the formation of an inner beliefs and impressions. Bigne Sanchez, and Sanjez [4] findings that pointed out that the image of a tourist destination for visitors to revisit the willingness to have a positive impact.

Tourist destination imagery will affect not only revisiting willingness also affect the perceived value of tourism [5] [6]. Although the above studies illustrate the image of the destination for tourists' perception of the importance of the tourism value, but for farm operators, tourists for environment perception towards Park, also decided important reference set of farm facilities and natural landscape. In fact, due to tourists during the tourism and recreation, will continue to interact with the surrounding environment, the feelings of the environment is very important, is the perception of the problem. In a related study also pointed out that "environmental perception" for "casual behavior" will have an impact [7]. Lin [8], the environmental perception refers to the individual preliminary environmental information gathered by the senses, such as vision, hearing, smell, and taste, people; any further take these feelings to understand the relationship between the individual and the environment. Xiao [9] study of environmental perception, the ecological park visitors to Danaiku tourists environment perception that organism for exposure to the environment, through feeling, attention and behavior, choose to receive definition stimuli in the environment, with the message, based on past experience, through a series of feelings, paraphrase, cognitive, psychological evaluation, etc. conversion, the psychological process of dealing with environmental messages. The Lai [7] finishing past and recreation related environmental perception research, found

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that the results of these studies are to a certain extent the environment on human perception, has engaged in activities on the environment as possible, a more positive the perception, feelings, will be higher willingness to continue to engage in will also increase. So from the above terms, the tourists for Leisure Farm perception of how well for its future revisiting willingness have an impact. In addition, in a related study, also confirmed that the attitude of tourists for environmental and recreation experience somewhat related [10] [11].

From the point of view of the leisure experience in the process of engaging in leisure activities, a person's senses, perception, mental and behavior will continue and the surrounding environment interaction between the feelings and experiences of the participants from those interactions. Participate in the process, the interaction between the mind and the environment arising from the experience, will affect its value for the travel experience. Tsao [12] pointed out, leading to the production and consumption of tourism products, tourism products with the indivisibility simultaneously, that is, tourists must be experienced in order to obtain the feelings and experience, it is necessary to let the tourists in all aspects satisfaction. The most commonly used by researchers, compared Clawson and Knetsch [13] distinguish recreational experience five phases, respectively, for the plan to go away, live events, backhaul and memories. Tourists' daily visit different attractions and activities engaged in, it will have a different experience, and the feel of this travel experience is good or not, will have an impact on their subsequent re-visiting willingness. Lee, Dattilo and Howard [14] study, recreation experience in addition to the positive experience negative (pressure and not unpleasant) of experience; while the negative and positive experience usually is simultaneous, so the recreation experience is not for a single perception. From the recreation experience course description factors affect tourists choose recreation areas of except tourists itself of travel motivation, past recreational experience, amusement recreation area, the environmental attributes cognitive considerations, which after the tourists to experience the satisfaction level, will cause visitors to the recreation area the whole image the experience accumulated with the next revisiting willingness.

For leisure farm operators, most expect is hope that visitors longer to farm consumption, so is very important to understand the factors of tourists farms revisiting willingness. According to the tourism and leisure studies pointed out that the impact of tourists revisiting willingness factors, including the destination image [4], for tourist sites "environmental perception" [14], tourist locations "experience" [15]. Based on the above, this study will travel destination imagery, environmental consciousness, and the point of view of the tourist experience, analyze the impact of the above factors revisiting willingness for tourists, and well-known tourist attractions Xinshe leisure agriculture park visitors, hope leisure Farm managers operating reference.

According to the research motivation, this study there is the purpose of the following two points: (A) analysis of visitors' tourism image Xinshe agricultural park, environmental

consciousness, travel experience, revisiting willingness relevant circumstances. (B) Based on the findings Xinshe agricultural parks and other recreational farms on the operation of the reference.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Subject and Sampling

This study used convenience sampling and visitors to the site to Xinshe leisure agriculture park travel survey. The survey locations mainly in the visitor center within the leisure agriculture visitors to assist in completing the questionnaire. Prior to the survey will be asked visitors whether completed the agricultural park attractions travel. If the answer is "Yes" and willing to cooperate with the investigation to be given a questionnaire to fill in; If the answer is "No" visitors do not investigate. The survey takes into account a questionnaire of 700 copies total recovery of 663 questionnaires were deducted 27 invalid questionnaires (fill in incomplete or answer exactly the same), 636 were validly questionnaire after.

B. Questionnaire

This research tool is divided into five parts, the first part of the tourist destination image scale, a total of 15 questions, mainly want to know the impression of tourists Xinshe leisure Agriculture Park, looking forward to the idea of environmental awareness, traffic, overall assessment feelings. This part of the Scale for the preparation of the farm research Chang and Lee [15], the main reference, as well as the researchers observed record farm environmental situation at the scene on the ground. The second part of the environmental perception scale, a total of 26 questions, mainly want to know the tourists for leisure agriculture park's natural landscape, hardware, and event planning cognition; prepared Scale reference Xiao [9] "environmental perception", as well as on-site observations, the researchers field records leisure agriculture park of the facilities and services. The third part of the recreational experience scale, a total of 13 questions, mainly want to know the senses of the tourists on leisure agriculture park headquarters component of emotion, thinking, action, associated, five dimensions, such as the situation [16]; table prepared, mainly with reference to Chen [17], Timor consumer experience, as well as researchers on the ground at the scene observed record farm environment and facilities circumstances. Fourth part of "the revisiting willingness Scale total of six questions; prepared for this part of the Scale reference Chang and Lee [15] study of the Great Lakes region, mainly want to know the views of visitors to re-visit, and recommended the wishes of others. Of the four scales, using the five-point Likert scale to measure, respectively, from "strongly disagree", "disagree", "normal", "agree", "agree", respectively, to give 1-5 scores. The fifth part of the personal data, including: gender, age, marital status, level of education, occupation, income, place of residence.

C. Data Analysis

In this study, the valid questionnaires using SPSS For Windows 18.0 statistical analysis, analysis steps include: 1. Exploratory factor analysis and Cronbach α reliability test of statistical methods to construct the reliability and validity of the

research tool. 2. Frequency distribution, percentage Xinshe leisure agriculture park tourists demographic variables assigned to analyze the case. 3. Used Pearson correlation analysis relationship between image, environmental consciousness, travel experience, and revisiting willingness. 4. Used multiple-regression analysis to understand the visitors to the park image, environmental perception, and travel experience on revisiting willingness predict ability.

D. Validity and Reliability Analysis

a. Validity Analysis

After exploratory factor analysis, this study's tourism image and scale extract four factors, according to the characteristics of each of the factors that are following options were named as "excellent facilities and services" and "relaxed atmosphere of space", "spacious paternity attractive, the scale of the outdoor space "as well as" negative image "cumulative variance of 67.20, 67.2% explained tourists explain Xinshe leisure agriculture park image. Environmental perception, the study of environmental perception scale analysis identified five factors, the characteristics of each of the factors that are following options were named as "good" public environmental equipment, building facilities in accordance with local environment "," ecological performances attract people" , "convenient transportation and comfortable, "as well as" fresh and clean feeling" the scale cumulative variance of 60.90, 60.9% explained tourists to Xinshe leisure agriculture park environment perception. Travel experience, the study of tourism experience scale extract three factors, according to the characteristics of each of the factors that are following options were named as "thinking associated with" emotional experience "and" action experience, this cumulative variance of 67.58, explained 67.58% visitors clear Xinshe leisure agriculture park the explanatory power of the travel experience. Revisiting willingness of this study revisiting willingness Scale extract two factors, each factor are following options features were named "the tourists top priority" and "happy to recommend to others.", The scale cumulative variation 62.75, interpretable tourists to Xinshe leisure agriculture park revisiting willingness explanatory power of 62.75%.

b. Reliability Analysis

The results of this analysis show that this study tourism image scale α value of .90; "environmental consciousness" Scale alpha value of .94; travel experience "Scale alpha value of .90; the revisiting willingness" Scale α value of .88; shown from the results of this study the scale has a high degree of reliability.

III. RESULTS

A. Demographic Information Analysis

In this study on the recovery of 636 valid questionnaires, Gender effective sample of 636 people, including 317 males and 319 women. The age of 21 to 30 ages, the numbers of the highest total of 321 people, at least in terms of age, which was 61 years of age who count 2 people? In marital status, the married is a total of 208 people, 428 unmarried people. Universities degree in educational attainment, which share the

largest number of total of 333 people, at least the total of 11 doctoral degrees. In terms of occupation, in which the number of students share the largest count 217 people, at least for the home tube, and 13 people. In personal monthly income, share of income less than \$ 20,000 (NT. dollar) the largest number of total of 245 people, a minimum of \$ 100,001 (NT. dollar) total.

B. Correlation Analysis of the Destination Image, Environmental Perception, Travel Experiences, and Revisiting Willingness

From the Table I a correlation analysis of the results shows that the tourists on the Xinshe leisure agriculture park "destination image" and "environmental perception" ($r = .77, p < .01$), as well as individuals in the park "travel experience" ($r = .65, p < .01$), and "revisiting willingness" ($r = .58, p < .01$), factors significantly positive correlation between the In addition, visitors to the park's "environmental perception" personal "travel experience" ($r = .75, p < .01$), as well as "revisiting willingness" ($r = .69, p < .01$) between the factors significantly positive correlation exists. The last tourists in the park "travel experience" and "revisiting willingness" ($r = .68, p < .01$) also significantly positive correlation between the factors.

TABLE I
CORRELATION OF THE DESTINATION IMAGE, ENVIRONMENTAL PERCEPTION, TRAVEL EXPERIENCES AND REVISITING WILLINGNESS

	Destination image	Environmenta 1 perception	Travel experiences	Revisiting willingness
Destination image	1			
Environmenta 1 perception	.770*	1		
Travel experiences	.650**	.743**	1	
Revisiting willingness	.589**	.669**	.685**	1

**p<.01

C. Regression Analysis of the Destination Image, Environmental Perception, Travel Experiences, on Revisiting Willingness

TABLE II
REGRESSION ANALYSIS OF THE DESTINATION IMAGE ON REVISITING WILLINGNESS

Variables	B	Std. Error	Beta	t-value	Sig
A	.246	.033	.276	7.426*	.000
B	.416	.070	.209	5.956*	.000
C	.359	.048	.287	7.455*	.000
D	.013	.067	.006	.190	.849
R = .608 R ² = .370 adjusted R ² = .366, F = 92.69*					

*p<.05

Note: A. excellent facilities and services

B. relaxed atmosphere of space

C. spacious paternity attractive, the scale of the outdoor space

D. negative image

Analysis of the results from Table II can be learned, "destination image" dimension, invested four predictive variables, including the "excellent facilities and services", the "relaxed atmosphere of space" and "spacious paternity

attractive, the scale of the outdoor space", the three factors of the significant level of explained variance revisiting willingness .37, and there are can predictable the revisiting willingness to achieve 37%. "Negative image" does not predict the role exists.

In Table III, the environmental perception dimensions the five predictor variable inputs (Public Environmental Facilities excellent facilities comply with the local environment, ecological performance attractive, convenient transportation and comfortable, fresh and natural feel) have reached the level of significance of revisiting willingness".468 explained variance forecast the revisiting willingness of 47%.

TABLE III
REGRESSION ANALYSIS OF THE ENVIRONMENTAL PERCEPTION ON REVISITING WILLINGNESS

Variables	B	Std. Error	Beta	t-value	Sig
A	.076	.024	.135	3.134*	.002
B	.317	.042	.313	7.554*	.000
C	.147	.042	.117	3.477*	.001
D	.157	.040	.162	3.960	.000
E	.197	.053	.135	3.688	.000
R =.634 R ² =.468 adjusted R ² =.464, F=110.828*					

*p<.05

Note: A. good public environmental equipment
B. building facilities in accordance with local environment
C. ecological performances attract people
D. convenient transportation and comfortable
E. fresh and clean feeling

View from Table IV analysis, the dimensions of the travel experience, invested three predictor variables, "thinking with associated" and "emotional experience" factor varying item up to a significant level, revisiting willingness explained variance of .49, the forecast the revisiting willingness of 49%.

TABLE IV
REGRESSION ANALYSIS OF THE TRAVEL EXPERIENCES ON REVISITING WILLINGNESS

Variables	B	Std. Error	Beta	t-value	Sig
A	.461	.030	.566	15.202*	.000
B	.286	.066	.152	4.365*	.000
C	.149	.088	.063	1.687	.092
R =.700 R ² =.490 adjusted R ² =.487, F=202.121*					

*p<.05

Note: A. thinking associated with
B. emotional experience
C. action experience

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Relationship of the Destination Image, Environmental Perception, Travel Experiences, and Revisiting Willingness

Destination image, perception of the environment, tourism experience and revisiting willingness factor analysis, the results showed a significant positive correlation between the variables. From the above results support the tourism and leisure studies have pointed out that the factors affecting the willingness of visitors to re-visit, including destination image [4], for tourist destinations and environmental perception" [14], the location of the travel experience "[15]. Xinshe leisure with agriculture park visitors and his perception of the farm environment;

further tourism experience, its future, the future will not come back Agriculture Park related.

In the regression analysis results, dimensions of the research in the destination image, invested a total of four predictive variables, where "good facilities and services", "relaxed atmosphere of space", "spacious the paternity outdoor space" Three factors variables revisiting willingness of the level of significance. Pointed out in by Qiu [18] study of the the Ilan four major farm in the composition of the tourism image dimensions, "Quality of Service", "parent-child outdoor activities, the space elements, positive emotions, negative emotions revisiting willingness to predict the results of this study and the case was more similar. From the results of this study can be learned leisure agriculture park facilities service quality, as well as with the parent-child facilities to tourists positive effect, then the visitors to re-visit will also be the higher. From the above results, can be found in the tourists would like to revisit the reasons Xinshe leisure agriculture park system in the process of leisure agriculture park tourism and recreation, the interaction of the fully feel with friends and family, others, and this interaction relationship to strengthen the relationship between each other. In fact, in terms of the results from the tourists who travel together, most of the tourists and students, friends, colleagues to Xinshe leisure agriculture park tourism tourists account for the largest number, followed by the family, this interactive experience, visitors again would like to re-visit the main cause.

Inputs in environmental perception five predictor variables (public environment facilities good facilities comply with the local environment, ecological performance attractive, convenient transportation and comfortable, fresh and natural feel) and all of the revisiting willingness significant level, the predictive power of 50%. Lai [7] finishing study and recreation related "environmental consciousness" in the past, and found that the results of these studies are the environment on human perception has to a certain extent, when the environment as possible, have engaged in activities will be higher perception of a more positive perception, and also increases the willingness to continue to engage in. From the above results, showing tourists Xinshe leisure agriculture park environment perception showing a positive attitude, and to ecosystem-based tourism region, home again attract tourists, provide products and services, hospitality services personnel services, as well as the environmental landscape maintenance, and sustains the willingness of tourists whether to revisit.

Put three predictive variables in terms of travel experience, thinking and association ", " emotional experience "factor variables revisiting willingness significant level. From the above results can be found in the tourists would like to revisit, therefore the Xinshe leisure agriculture park tourism see everyday never seen a sheep show, the beautiful scenery of the journey and artifacts caused inspired by Lenovo or inspiration, as well as a rich and exciting trip, plus see the beautiful scenery and cultural relics to make them feel happy, the tourists would like to once again revisit one of the main reasons.

B. Suggestions

Based on the above analysis, the study suggests Xinshe leisure agriculture park tourism image and environmental

perception, the quality of the tourism experience and revisiting willingness for the park in terms of promotion of tourism marketing must explicitly create the characteristics of the place. To allow visitors to understand to tourism and recreation in the region may seek service "facilities" "ecological performance attractive", "facilities comply with the local environment, a spacious parent-child outdoor space" of the experience; When these experiences are met, can improve its revisiting willingness. In addition, this study found that "excellent facilities and services", "ecological performance attractive", "facilities in line with the local environment", "spacious the paternity outdoor space", the four factors of tourism image, the most influential of revisiting willingness force. It is suggested that Xinshe leisure industry, tourism marketing promotion, shall strengthen local diversity and innovation, in order to enhance the visibility and increase the amount of tourists visitors must continuously improve the service quality of the staff and to strengthen the maintenance of the landscape and recreation development of resources to help the tourists to travel at a later date to Xinshe Farm. Other tourist destination image factor for subsequent researchers, the Institute invested, forecasts, "the revisiting willingness predicts high. The main reason may be prepared Questionnaire, and the subjects in the sample problem. It is suggested that future researchers during the study, prepared Scale longer in line with local conditions; specific or thinking about expanding research tourists' entire Xinshe leisure agriculture park tourism image, in order to study the results of more explicit.

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